
EVALUATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION LEARNING FOR CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSION-BASED ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN SINDANG PLAINS DISTRICT, REJANG LEBONG REGENCY, BENGKULU PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine the results of evaluating the context, input, process, product of the implementation of Physical Education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based elementary schools in Sindang Darat District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province. The evaluation model used in this research is the CIPP model. The results of the research show that the evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in onclusion-based elementary schools in Sindang Plains District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province, results in the poor category. Next, each aspect of the evaluation is explained, namely. (1) Context evaluation is in the good category. Indicators of learning materials and formulation of objectives were 3.14 in the good category. (2) Input evaluation is in 3.29 the good category. (3) Process evaluation results are in the poor category. (4) Product evaluation in 1.83 in the poor category.

Keywords- Children with Special Needs, Evaluation, Physical Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaluation is an inseparable thing in measuring the success or feasibility of a program or policy issued by those who have the authority in this case, namely the government (Akbar & M ohi, 2020, p.118). In another sense, policy evaluation is an activity designed to assess the results of different government programs specifically in terms of conformity with predetermined criteria, as well as having a real impact on the audience as desired.

Evaluation can later help in determining policies at the policy assessment stage of the policy-making process and provide appropriate information about the achievement of policy objectives. Evaluation not only produces conclusions about how far the problem has been resolved, but also contributes to clarification and criticism of the values underlying the policy, helping to adjust and reformulate the problem Dunn, (2003, p.24).

Education is the right of every citizen, meaning that citizens are entitled to a proper education. Every individual is entitled to education services regardless of their condition. Social, economic and health disabilities, both physical and mental, are not a reason for reducing education (Abdullah, 2013, p. 196).

Social and economic inability, for example, the child comes from a family with a socially capable or less capable status, while the health condition in question is that the child is declared healthy or has a physical or mental disability, as a citizen of the Republic of Indonesia, these circumstances do not eliminate their right to education Abdullah, (2013, p. 204).

The birth conditions of each child are not always the same as what is expected. In some cases, the expected child born with more genetic characteristics than their parents are actually born different. Differences such as limb deficiencies, deficiencies in intelligence or even blessed with above-average intelligence, thus requiring special guidance in accordance with their abilities. Children like this can be called children with special needs, because they have abnormalities in terms of physical, mental and social behavior characteristics (Desiningrum, 2016).

Children with special needs are isolated from social life. Society assumes that they do not play a role, do not socialize and cannot do their job like normal children. Basically, children with special needs have the same opportunities as normal children to self-actualize, it's just that many people doubt the ability of children with special needs Rahardja, (2017, pp. 7-11).

The government provides special education for students with special needs with specially designed and built learning designs in various regions in the form of special schools (SLB), although it does not reach remote areas. These educational services are still very few, so the opportunities for children with disabilities are minimal and seem neglected in the formal world. In addition to the existence of special schools that do not reach remote areas, the high cost of school fees is also an obstacle to children with special needs obtaining proper education. This made the government come up with a new idea, namely the existence of inclusive education so that children with special needs can more easily get educational services like normal children in general Ilahi, Smart, 2013, pp.27-30).

Inclusive education is an innovative and strategic education to expand access to education for all children with special needs. This education is implemented in regular schools, the aim is that children with special needs can socialize with normal

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children in the surrounding environment and train normal children to appreciate their special needs. differences so that both can coexist (Mahabbati, 2013).

Inclusive schools use a modified regular school curriculum, such as the results of research from Sukmawati (2014), that the curriculum used as a reference in learning physical education for students with special needs is a modified curriculum. Physical education materials given to students with special needs are the same as regular students, except that the level of difficulty is lowered.

Learning planning in inclusive schools is in accordance with the circumstances of the students. As the results of research from Nurussalihah (2016), that in inclusive schools using the KTSP curriculum and in the implementation of physical education refers more to an individualized approach. The implementation of the inclusive approach in learning from the results of Kharisma's research (2017), states that a manifestation of a series of efforts to educate and teach students is by exploring existing potential, with efforts to adjust the curriculum, strategies, methods, media and infrastructure as learning support.

Inclusive education is expected to harmonize the curriculum, facilities and infrastructure as well as a learning system that suits the conditions of students with special needs. The implementation of inclusive education is a concern for the right to education for children with special needs. Researchers found the problem that there is no definite learning evaluation standard for children who have advantages and disadvantages, even though they receive education services in inclusive classes at primary schools in Sindang Dataran sub-district, Rejang Lebong district, Bengkulu province.

Therefore, this research aims to find a solution to the problem of how the learning evaluation planning system, the form of evaluation, the form of reporting the results of the evaluation contained in the inclusion class, the focus of the research was carried out at an Inclusion-Based Primary School in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province.

The data obtained from the Rejang Lebong Regency Education Office Children with special needs in this school consist of several categories, namely tunagrahita, slow learner, and socio-emotional.

Evaluation is an effort to determine the level of implementation of a policy carefully by knowing the effectiveness of each component. Context, Input, Process, Product (CIPP) evaluation is the CIPP evaluation model in implementation is more widely used by evaluators, this is because this evaluation model is more comprehensive when compared to other evaluation models (Rocha, et al., 2021, pp. 1-19). The CIPP model is consistent in principle with the committee's definition of educational program evaluation as a level to describe achievement and provide information for alternative decision-making. Context evaluation involves analyzing issues related to

program environment or objective conditions to be implemented. It contains an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of a particular object. Input evaluation provides effective planning for the successful implementation of the curriculum. The main orientation of input evaluation is to propose a plan that can achieve what the institution wants. Process evaluation (process) can only be done if the curriculum innovation has been implemented. Evaluation of results (product) is to determine the extent to which the implemented curriculum has been able to meet the needs of groups that use after the program runs and the level of success that has been achieved or what will be produced.

One of the steps to achieve the learning objectives of PJOK is to know how high the performance of the components that support the PJOK learning program, especially for children with special needs by evaluating the components of these components.

II. METHOD

Type of Research

This type of research is evaluation research that uses mixed quantitative and qualitative methods. Sukmadinata (2017, p. 68) states that evaluative research is a research activity that evaluates an activity/program which aims to measure the success of an activity/program and determine the success of a program and whether it is as expected. This research is also directed at assessing the success of the benefits, usefulness, contribution and feasibility of a program of activities of a particular unit / institution. This research refers to a systematic scientific procedure carried out to measure the results of a program or project (the effectiveness of a program) in accordance with the planned objectives or not, by collecting, analyzing and reviewing the implementation of the program carried out objectively. Then formulate and determine policies by first considering the positive values and benefits of a program. Based on the above opinion, this research is able to obtain real data in accordance with the results of the evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in Inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province.

The evaluation model that will be used in this research is the CIPP model because the CIPP model is a complex evaluation that includes Context, Input, Process, and Product. The CIPP model is seen as one of the most comprehensive evaluation models, meaning that it can obtain more accurate and objective information.

Place and Time of Evaluation

This evaluation was conducted in inclusion-based public primary schools in Rejang lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province, totaling 6 schools. The evaluation time was conducted from

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November-December 2023. Data on inclusion-based public primary schools in Sindang Dataran sub-district, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province are shown in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. Data and Addresses of Inclusion-Based Public Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran Subdistrict, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province.

No	School Name	Address
1	SDN 84 Rejang Lebong	Desa Dataran Air Rusa 2
2	SDN 142 Rejang Lebong	Desa Airusa 1
3	SDN 143 Rejang Lebong	Desa IV Suku Menanti
4	SDN 132 Rejang Lebong	Desa Bengko
5	SDN 153 Rejang Lebong	Desa Talang Belitar
6	SDN 164 Rejang Lebong	Desa Warung Pojok

Research Subjects

Table 2: Research subjects at inclusive primary schools in Sindang Dataran sub-district, Rejang Lebong district, Bengkulu province.

NO	School Name	Head School	Teacher	Students
1	SDN 84 Rejang Lebong	1	1	3
2	SDN 142 Rejang Lebong	1	1	2
3	SDN 143 Rejang Lebong	1	1	6
4	SDN 132 Rejang Lebong	1	1	4
5	SDN 153 Rejang Lebong	1	1	3
6	SDN 164 Rejang Lebong	1	1	4
	Total	6	6	22

Data Collection Technique

Data collection techniques are used to collect data according to the research procedures so that the required data is obtained. Sugiyono (2017, p. 224) states that data collection techniques are the most strategic step in research, because the main purpose of research is to collect data. In simple terms, data collection is defined as a process or activity carried out by researchers to reveal or capture various phenomena, information or conditions of the research location in accordance with the scope of the research. Another opinion according to Budiwanto (2017, p. 183) states that data collection methods are techniques or methods used to collect data.

The data collection technique refers to a method, the form of which is shown in its use in collecting data using questionnaire instruments, interviews, observations, tests, documentation and so on. Meanwhile, data collection instruments are tools used to collect data. Because it is a tool, the instrument can be a check list sheet, questionnaire guidelines, interview guidelines, observation guidelines, photo cameras and other instruments.

The steps taken in collecting data in this study are as follows. (1) Researchers made observations in each SDN school in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province regarding the implementation of physical education

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learning for children with special needs. (2) Researchers documented the learning process while in the school environment, and infrastructure in Physical Education Learning. (3) Researchers asked for a research permit. (4) Researchers gave research instruments in the form of questionnaires to subjects who became research samples directly. (4) Researchers conducted interviews with subjects who became samples. (5) Researchers recorded and summarized the results of the data obtained.

Research Instruments

Research instruments according to Hardani, et al., (2020, p. 284) is “a measuring tool used to obtain quantitative information about variations in variable characteristics objectively, so it is necessary to develop a scale or measuring instrument to measure variables in more systematic data collection”. The instrument emphasizes its meaning and understanding as a tool for collecting and obtaining the necessary data (Budiwanto, 2017, p. 183). These instruments will be used to obtain data on the evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in SDN Se- Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province.

a. Observation

Observation is an effort to collect data when researchers go directly to the field to observe the behavior and activities of individuals at the research site (Creswell & Poth, 2016, p. 42). Observation in a study is defined as focusing attention on an object by involving all the senses to get data. So observation is a direct observation using sight, smell, hearing, touch, or if necessary with taste. Instruments used in observation can be in the form of observation guidelines, tests, questionnaires, image recordings, and sound recordings. Observation instruments in the form of observation guidelines are usually used in systematic observation where the observer works according to the guidelines that have been made. The guidelines contain a list of types of activities that are likely to occur or activities to be observed (Siyoto & Sodik, 2015, p. 82). Observations were made by researchers by observing and recording the implementation of learning.

b. Interview

Interview is a data collection technique by which researchers can conduct face-to-face interviews with participants (Creswell & Poth, 2016, p. 48). Furthermore Sugiyono (2017, p. 317) defines an interview as a meeting between two people to exchange information and ideas through questions and answers, so that meaning can be constructed in a certain topic. Herdiansyah (2015, p. 31) states that an interview is a process of communication interaction conducted by at least two people, on the basis of availability and in a natural setting, where the direction of the conversation refers to a predetermined goal by prioritizing trust as the main foundation in the process of understanding. In this study, interviews were conducted with all research respondents. Interviews will be conducted with PJOK teachers, Principals, Students.

c. Documentation

There are two types of documentation instruments, namely documentation guidelines that contain outlines or categories for which data will be sought, and check-lists that contain a list of variables for which data will be collected. The difference between these two forms of instruments lies in the intensity of the symptoms studied. In the documentation guideline, the researcher simply writes a check mark in the symptom column, while in the check-list, the researcher gives a tally on each symptom occurrence (Siyoto & Sodik, 2015, p. 82).

Documentation is used to strengthen the data obtained by interviews and direct observation and data collection techniques. This is to complement the lack of data from observations, interviews and questionnaires. The documentation in question relates to the school profile, the list of students' grades, the attendance list of students, the teaching plan/RPP made by the teacher, the form and type of learning evaluation, and the results of the assessment. The documentation guidelines are made in the form of a check list.

d. Questionnaire

Siyoto & Sodik (2015, p. 79) questionnaire is a data collection method, the instrument is called according to the name of the method. The form of the questionnaire sheet can be a number of written questions, the aim is to obtain information from the respondent about what he experiences and knows. Sugiyono (2017, p. 162) argues that a questionnaire is a data collection technique that is done by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer.

The questionnaire used is a closed questionnaire. Arikunto's opinion (2015, p. 102-103) that a closed questionnaire is a questionnaire that is presented in such a form that the respondent only needs to give a check list (√) in the appropriate column or place, with a direct questionnaire using a graded scale. The questionnaire was made by the researcher himself with the questions adjusted to the instrument grid that had been made previously based on the literature review and then validated by experts who were considered to understand this type of research. The questionnaire used is in the form of a rating scale, with a scale range of 1-4. After making the statement items, then the research conducted validation to expert lecturers.

Data Analysis Technique

1. Quantitative

Quantitative analysis serves to describe or describe the object under study through sample or population data as it is, without analyzing and making general conclusions (Sugiyono, 2017, p. 29). After all the data is collected, the next step is to analyze the data, so that the data can be drawn a conclusion with category calculations. The data obtained is then processed

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with the help of the SPSS version 20 computer program. Calculation of data analysis by finding the relative frequency percentage. With the following formula (Sudijono, 2015, p. 40):

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

Keterangan:

P= Persentase

F= Frequency

N= Number of Respondents

2. Qualitative

In accordance with the research objectives, the data analysis technique used to analyze the data in this study is an interactive qualitative analysis model as proposed by Miles and Huberman (in Sugiyono, 2017, p. 78), namely as follows.

a). Data Collection

Data obtained from observations, interviews and documentation are recorded in field notes which consist of two aspects, namely description and reflection. Description notes are natural data that contains what is seen, heard, felt, witnessed and experienced by the researcher without any opinions and interpretations from the researcher about the phenomena encountered. Reflection notes are notes that contain impressions, comments and interpretations of researchers about the findings encountered and are material for data collection plans for the next stage. To get this record, the researcher conducted several informant interviews.

b). Data Reduction

Data reduction is a process of selection, focusing, simplification and abstraction. How to reduce data is by making selections, making summaries or brief descriptions, classifying into patterns by making research transcripts to emphasize, shorten make focus, discard unimportant parts and organize so that conclusions can be drawn.

c). Data Display (Presentation of Data)

Presentation of data is a set of information arranged so that it provides the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action. So that the presentation of data does not deviate from the main problem, data presentation can be realized in the form of matrices, graphics, networks or charts as a guide to what information is happening. Data is presented in accordance with what was researched. d). Conclusions / Verifying (Drawing Conclusions)

Drawing conclusions is an attempt to find or understand meaning, regularity of explanatory patterns, causal flow or propositions. effect or proposition. The conclusions drawn are immediately verified by looking and questioning again while looking at field notes in order to obtain a more precise understanding, besides that it can also be done by discussing. This is done so that the data obtained and the interpretation of the data have validity, so that the conclusions drawn become solid.

Determining the validity of data, researchers need to convey the steps taken to check the reliability and validity of the results of their research. According to Gibbs (Creswell & Poth, 2016, p. 53), qualitative reliability is an approach that researchers use consistently if applied by other researchers for different projects.

Success Criteria

Determining success criteria is very important in evaluation activities because without criteria, an evaluator will have difficulty in considering a decision. Without criteria, the consideration that will be given has no basis. Therefore, determining the criteria that will be used will make it easier for evaluators to consider the value or price of the program components they assess, whether they are in accordance with what was previously determined or not.

Success criteria need to be created by the evaluator because the evaluator consists of several people who need agreement in assessing. Other broader and more justifiable reasons include:

1. With benchmarks, the evaluator can better assess the object to be assessed because there is a benchmark to follow.
2. The benchmarks that have been made can be used to answer or account for the results of the assessment that has been carried out if there are people who want to learn more or even want to review it.
3. Benchmark criteria are used to minimize the non-subjective elements of the assessment. With the criteria, in conducting an evaluation, the evaluator is required by these criteria and follows each item as a reference so that it is not based on personal opinion.
4. Criteria or benchmarks will provide direction to the evaluator if there is more than one evaluator, so that the criteria are interpreted together.

No	Interval	Criteria
1	3,26-4,00	Very Good
2	2,51-3,25	Good
3	1,76-2,50	Less
4	1,00-1,75	Very Less

Table 3. Success Criteria

III. RESEARCH RESULT

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1. Context Evaluation

Indicator	Head School	Teacher PJOK	Total	Mean	Category
Learning materials and formulation of objectives	3,17	3,11	6,28	3,14	Good
Organizing materials, media and other learning resources	3,00	2,56	5,56	2,78	Good
Designing teaching and learning activities	3,28	3,39	6,67	3,34	Very Good
Class Management	3,44	3,22	6,66	3,33	Very Good
Assessment	3,37	3,33	6,70	3,35	Very Good
context component				3,19	Good

Table 4. Average results of evaluation context for contemporary education learning for ABK.

2. Input Evaluation

Indicator	Head School	Teacher PJOK	Total	Mean	Category
Suitability of learning materials with KI and objectives	3,25	3,33	6,58	3,29	Good
Learner Characteristics	2,33	2,48	4,81	2,41	Less
Input component				2,85	Good

Table 5. Average Results of Evaluation Input for the Implementation of Physical Education Learning for ABK

3. Process Evaluation

Indicator	Head School	Teacher PJOK	Total	Mean	Category
Learning Activities	2,30	-	2,30	2,30	Less
Activity learners	1,75	1,97	1,86	1,86	Less
Process component				2,08	Less

Table 6. Average Results of Evaluation Process Indicators for the Implementation of Physical Education Learning in Inclusion-based State Elementary School ABKs in Sindang Plains District

4. Product Evaluation

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Indicator	Head School	Teacher PJOK	Total	Mean	Category
Learning Results					Less
	1,72	1,93	3,65	1,83	
Product component				1,83	Less

Table 7. Average Results of Physical Education Learning Evaluation Products for Children with Special Needs

Discussion

Program evaluation is a systematic and subjective assessment of an object, program or policy that is ongoing or has been completed, both in its implementation design and results, where the purpose of program evaluation is to determine the relevance and achievement of goals, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability, where an evaluation must provide reliable and useful information to be able to take lessons for the decision-making process. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the evaluation of the physical education learning implementation program for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province, the results are in the insufficient category.

The lack of implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in the Sindang Dataran District of Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province is due to several obstacles. The obstacles faced by teachers and parents in assisting children to learn as described, namely the lack of understanding about children with tunagrahita and materials that can make children with tunagrahita understand it, the difficulty of parents in assisting children to learn.

It is hoped that in the future this will no longer be an obstacle in learning at school and at home for children so that children are able to get optimal learning services, because good and optimal services for children in learning are the main key to successful learning goals (Wardani & Ayriza, 2021, p. 779). 779).

1. Context Evaluation

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province is good.

Context evaluation is a description and specification of the program environment, unmet needs, population and sample characteristics of the individuals served and the objectives of the program itself. In other words, context evaluation is an evaluation of needs, the purpose of meeting needs, and the characteristics of the individual handling (evaluator) (Gandomkar, 2018, p. 95; Umam & Saripah, 2018, p. 20).

Indicators of learning materials and formulation of objectives amounted to 3.14 in the good category. The teachers prepare lesson plans in accordance with the competency standards and core competencies contained in the guidelines. From the SK-KD, sports teachers compile indicators that are in accordance with the conditions of students with special needs, including the selection of materials and learning principles that are tailored to the conditions of students. This is also confirmed by research from Paradipta & Dewantoro (2019) which states that each type of disorder or problem faced by children with special needs requires different services.

requires different services. Likewise in physical education, each type of disorder requires its own form of physical education service. Therefore, ideally the physical education program is an individual service program.

2. Input evaluation

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the input evaluation of the program for evaluating the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province is good.

Haryanto (2020, p. 97); Gunung & Darma (2019, p. 34).

Darma (2019, p. 34); Sopha & Nanni (2019, p. 136) explain that input evaluation provides information about selected inputs, points of strength and weakness, strategies, and designs for realizing goals. Santiyadnya (2021, p. 4) explains that the purpose is to help organize decisions, determine what alternative sources will be taken, what are the plans and strategies to achieve the needs, and what are the work procedures to achieve them. The input evaluation component itself consists of several, namely human resources, supporting facilities and equipment, funds or budgets, and various procedures and rules needed. Indicators of learner characteristics of 2.41 in less. This is indicated by the lack of enthusiasm of students during learning, participants do not understand every lesson, some students are late for school, students also feel bored quickly with learning due to lack of appropriate material. These results are supported in the research of Bahasoan, et al., (2020); Suryaman, et al., (2020); Tratnik, et al., (2019); Jack, et al., (2018) that students are less enthusiastic in learning. that students

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are less enthusiastic in learning. In the learning process carried out at school, all elements of education are asked to be able to provide effective learning facilities for students.

3. Process Evaluation

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the process of evaluating the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusive-based primary schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province, the results are in the insufficient category. Indicators of learning activities amounted to 2.30 in the deficient category. In the implementation of special learning for children with disabilities, there are often obstacles or discrepancies with the learning that should be.

Many assume that the responsibility of teachers in carrying out special learning for children with special needs is much lighter than learning for other children (Semradova & Hubackova, 2016, p. 11; Budi Lestari, et al., 2021, p. 3; Wahyuni, et al., 2021). Moreover, Syahfitri et al., (2020, p. 3) explained that special learning carried out by teachers is currently limited to knowledge transfer activities. Students lack deep understanding, decline in thinking levels and the inability of teachers to see the extent to which teaching material can influence behavior is a new challenge for teachers to understand each learner.

The indicator of learner activities is 1.86 in the insufficient category. Not all students or do every lesson the teacher provides. Specialized learning that requires support is not without problems that will hinder the learning process. Carrying out special learning requires facilities that support and meet the standards of children with special needs. As stated by Lestari & Gunawan (2020: pp. 59); Garaus (2018, p.

447); Alalwan, et al., (2018, p. 100) Another obstacle found is the ability of parents to provide special education facilities for children with special needs, such as the use of special equipment.

educational facilities for children with special needs such as the use of learning equipment and which requires a lot of money (Zara, et al., 2020, p. 70; Lone, et al., 2020).

4. Product Evaluation

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the evaluation of the program for evaluating the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based public elementary schools in the Sindang Dataran sub-district of Rejang Lebong Regency is 1.83 in the insufficient category.

Facts in the field, show that all students get the maximum score when given questions at home not at school. This is a question for teachers, whether students really understand the material or students get help from adults when doing assignments. Teachers cannot objectively assess learning achievement according to students' abilities. From the affective side, teachers also experience difficulties in assessment.

Similarly, organizing online learning requires a lot of money, needing various supporting components such as gadgets, electricity, and so on. Overcoming these obstacles, teachers should implement a manual learning program, namely home visits, namely learning visits from home to home (Atsani, 2020, p. 82; Nadeak, 2020: p. 176; Usman & Huda, 2021, p. 3; Mantara, et al., 2020, p. 446). The findings above are also reinforced by views that say that it is not only able to portray obstacles from the perspective of students, but it can also highlight the aspects of teachers, through learning, teachers can improve their professionalism in the field of specialization in children with different needs, teachers will be more skilled in providing learning materials for children with disabilities (Jamilah, 2020, p. 238; Cahapay, 2020, p. 4;

Moyo, 2020, p. 536).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research and the results of the data analysis that has been carried out, it is concluded that the evaluation of the implementation of adaptive physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province the results are in the insufficient category. Furthermore, each evaluation aspect is explained as follows.

1. Context evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province is in the good category. Indicators of learning materials and formulation of objectives of 3.14 in the good category, organizing materials, learning media, and other learning resources of 2.78 in the good category, designing teaching and learning activities of 3.34 in the very good category, classroom management of 3.33 in the very good category, and assessment of 3.35 in the very good category.

2. Input evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based public elementary schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province is good. Indicators of suitability of learning materials with KI and Learning objectives of 3.29 in the good category and the characteristics of students of 2.41 in the less.

3. Process evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based public elementary schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province the results are in the less category. Indicators of learning activities amounted to 2.30 in the deficient category and student activities amounted to 1.86 in the deficient category.

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4. Product evaluation of the implementation of physical education learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based public elementary schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province the results are in the insufficient category. Indicators of achievement learning outcomes in inclusion-based State Elementary Schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province amounted to 1.83 in the insufficient category.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following suggestions can be given.

1. The CIPP evaluation should be applied by inclusion-based public elementary schools in Sindang Dataran Sub-district, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province so that it can be taken into consideration in making decisions related to PE learning for children with special needs.

2. Teachers should continue to develop knowledge by attending special trainings to develop the characteristics of children with other special needs, so that they can implement effective PE learning for children with special needs.

3. Schools should provide support both in the form of policies and in the form of adequate sports facilities and infrastructure that can support PE learning for children with special needs in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province.

4. This study evaluates the implementation of PE learning for children with special needs in inclusion-based public elementary schools in Sindang Dataran District, Rejang Lebong Regency, Bengkulu Province, future researchers should be able to research the analysis of the motor development of each child with all their disabilities in special needs schools throughout Indonesia, so that it can be used as a guideline for school principals and PE teachers in developing effective PE learning, especially for children with special needs.

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